

“EFFECT OF CORE STABILIZATION EXERCISES ON FINE MOTOR SKILLS IN DENTISTS- A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL STUDY”

Chaitanya A. Kulkarni
Community Physiotherapy Department
Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Physiotherapy,
Dr. D. Y. Patil Vidyapeeth
Pune, India

Sakshi M. Mhase
Community Physiotherapy Department
Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Physiotherapy,
Dr. D. Y. Patil Vidyapeeth
Pune, India

Navneet Mehta
Community Physiotherapy Department
Dr. D. Y. Patil College of Physiotherapy,
Dr. D. Y. Patil Vidyapeeth
Pune, India

Abstract: Fine motor skills are crucial for dentists to perform precise clinical procedures. Core stabilization exercises have been shown to enhance postural control and functional movement, potentially improving fine motor performance. However, their direct impact on dentists has not been extensively studied. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of the core stabilization exercise program on fine motor skills and core strength in practicing dentists. A pre-post intervention study was conducted with 30 dentists aged 20-60 years. Fine motor skills were assessed using the Finger Dexterity Test Board. Core strength was measured through manual muscle testing (MMT). Participants underwent a structured core stabilization exercise program, consisting of Abdominal in-drawing, pelvic bridging, single knee to chest, and bird dog exercises for 6 days a week for 3 weeks. Statistical analysis was performed using paired and unpaired t-tests, with significance set at $p < 0.001$. Following the intervention, participants demonstrated significant improvements in fine motor skills as measured by the Finger Dexterity test ([pre: 10.03 ± 1.10] vs. [post: 8.73 ± 1.01]), $p < 0.001$. Core strength also increased significantly across the muscle groups tested ($p < 0.001$). Core stabilization exercises effectively enhance fine motor skills and core strength in dentists. Incorporating such exercises into routine practice may improve clinical performance and reduce occupational fatigue.

KEYWORDS: Core stabilization, fine motor skills, dentists, rehabilitation, manual dexterity

INTRODUCTION

Dental professionals strive to prioritize oral health and ensure a safe environment for dental care. The Dental professionals have to work with precise hand movements and use vibrating dental instruments while treating patients. This often leads to compromising their own physical well-being, as they adopt awkward postures and experience tense muscles during the course of their work (1). Dentists need to perform precise work during dental prophylaxis, particularly during manual scaling, where they use high levels of force and precision to remove hard calculus from small areas of the tooth. Dentists depend on small, precise movements, often utilizing their thumb, index and middle finger to grip (2). Throughout their work day, dentists maintain a prolonged, immobile position. Since half of the body's muscles contract statically, there is very little movement within the spine even when the person

is seated correctly. These minor alteration lead to a number of musculoskeletal conditions affecting the shoulders, back, and neck (3). Improper posture often causes musculoskeletal disorders in dentists, which may lead to a reduction in their working hours and prompt early retirement. This can also increase fatigue and injuries and lead to reduction in patient satisfaction (4). Musculoskeletal disorders frequently start during university years (5) and is a problem faced by 64-93% of dentists (6,7) and 61-85% dental students (8,9). Similar to surgeons, a dentist utilizes both hands: while one hand carries out accurate drilling or another procedure, the other hand provides assistance. For instance, when drilling the maxillary teeth using indirect vision, the non-dominant hand needs to position the mirror at the exact yet flexible angle necessary for the dentists to have a clear view of the small, inverted working field. Acquiring this skill is regarded as quite challenging due to difficulty the brain faces in managing two distinct actions simultaneously performed by both the hands. This ability is characterized as “bi-manual coordination of continuous tasks.” Performing clinical dentistry is complex due to the necessity of combining a wide range of theoretical understanding with various skills, including fine motor abilities, hand-eye coordination, perception and precision (10). The majority of anatomy is situated within a restricted and hidden space of the oral cavity. For a successful treatment outcome, the physician must possess sufficient knowledge along with proficient manual skills. To develop exceptional manual skills, mastering manual dexterity is essential. Manual dexterity refers to the capability to skilfully use both hands in a coordinated manner to handle and manipulate objects, showcasing fine, precise movements. To become a proficient dentist, an individual must demonstrate the ability to perform with accuracy on a very small scale (11). The term “core stability” refers to the ability to stabilize core muscles, specifically in the lumbo pelvic region of the body. Maintaining stability in this area is crucial as it provides a foundation for the movement of the upper and lower extremities, helps support loads, and protects the spinal cord and nerve root. The major muscles involved in core stability include transverse abdominis, internal and external oblique, multifidus, erector spinae, rectus abdominis, and diaphragm.

In addition, the minor muscles such as latissimus dorsi, trapezius, and gluteus maximus also play a role in maintaining core stability (12). Rehabilitation practitioners commonly believe that the control and alignment of the trunk have a significant impact on the functioning of the extremities and the performance of everyday activities. The dynamic stability of shoulder girdle on a steady trunk is crucial for carrying out upper extremity functions like reaching, grasping, and manipulating objects (13). The core region plays a vital role in maintaining posture and refining precise movements in the arms and the legs. According to research on anatomical connections, the kinetic chain model, and the relationship between postural control and the upper extremity in the central nervous system, there appears to be a link between motor skills in the upper extremities and the core region. Additionally, it has been suggested that engaging in core stabilization exercises can enhance trunk stability and control, leading to improved postural stability and more skilful motor movements in the extremities (14).

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY-

The Institutional Ethical Committee clearance was obtained with IEC no. DYPCPT/ISEC/61/2024, and have also registered with the Clinical Trial Registry India (CTRI) with registration no. CTRI/2024/11/077061. The patients who fulfil the inclusion criteria was selected from Dr. D. Y. Patil University in , Pune. The verbal consent was taken from participants before allocating them. Based on purposive sampling, the participants were included in the study. The carefully monitored exercise program included 20 minutes of core stabilization exercise program. In the first week, the participants performed complete Isolated contractions of transversus abdominis and lumbar multifidus with abdominal drawing-in maneuver along with co-contraction of transversus abdominis and lumbar multifidus muscles. In the second and third weeks, the participants completed bridging, bird-dog position, and single knee-to-chest exercises.

Core stabilization exercise protocol – (13,15-18)

1st week protocol

- 1) Isolated contraction of transversus abdominis and lumbar multifidus with abdominal drawing-in manoeuvre (ADIM) in combination with contraction of pelvic floor muscles in minimum loading positions, such as prone or sitting positions.
-To activate Transversus Abdominis (TrA), the participants will be positioned in prone lying on a bed with a small pillow placed under their ankles
The participants will be asked to draw their lower anterior abdominal wall “up and-in” towards the spine.
-Isolated activation of Lumbar Multifidus (LM) will be stimulated by asking the participants to raise the

contralateral arm when performing ADIM seated on a chair.

(10 repetitions with 10 second hold) (6 days a week)

2nd and 3rd week protocol

- 2) Exercise difficulty will be increased by integrating deep muscle co-contraction with controlling movement of extremities and heavier loading positions-
 - i. Bridging-The participant will adopt a prone elbow position. The participant will raise his/her body onto the forearms, placed below the shoulders and toes. The participant will maintain his/her hips and back in a parallel straight-line posture.
(10 Second contraction hold and 10 repetitions) (6 days a week for 2 weeks)
 - ii. Bird-dog position -: The participant will lift right arm and left leg, holding the posture with an abdominal contraction for 10 s. Next, the left arm and right leg will be lifted.
(10 repetitions) (6 days a week for 2 weeks)
 - iii. Single knee to chest- The participants will lie supine on the plinth. They will then be instructed to let a leg fall off the table or bed, bend their other leg and wrap their hands around the bent knee, and pull the bent leg toward their chest.
(10 second contraction hold and 10 repetitions) (6 days a week for 2 weeks)

A 30 s rest between repetitions and a 60 s rest after each set will be provided.

RESULTS

The data was put into a Microsoft Excel sheet once it was coded. The computation of means and SD was part of descriptive statistics. Inferential statistics using the student’s paired test (for the quantitative data to compare pre and post-observation) and unpaired t-test (for quantitative data to compare within two groups) were used for comparison of all clinical indicators. The software used in the analysis was SPSS 27.0 version. The results were concluded to be highly statistically significant with $p < 0.001$.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS-

Table 1: Pre and Post Comparison of Manual Muscle a Strength of Core Muscles

		Mean	N	SD	SD Error Mean	P value
MMT	Pre	3.27	30	0.45	0.08	<0.001
	Post	4.20	30	0.41	0.08	

Figure 1: MMT Pre and Post Treatment

Table 1 and Figure 1: Indicates the MMT of core muscles prior and after the application of Core Stabilizing Exercises in the Dentists. Comparison of the above values is carried out through Paired t-test. The Paired t-test yields result by comparison of the two sets of data that are related to each other as in this case the comparison of the MMT of core muscles pre and post treatment. The small p-value < 0.001 indicates a significant difference between the two sets of values which is highly statistically significant. It means that the observed difference in the MMT of Core muscle pre and post measurements is unlikely to be due to random chance alone. Which in turn depicts that the core stabilization exercises provided are effective.

Table 2: Pre and Post Comparison of Finger Dexterity Test

		Mean	N	SD	SD Error Mean	P value
Finger Dexterity Test	Pre	10.03	30	1.10	0.20	<0.001
	Post	8.73	30	1.01	0.18	

Figure 2: Finger Dexterity Pre and Post Treatment

Table 2 and Figure 2: Represents the Finger Dexterity Pre and Post core stabilization exercises. The mean Finger dexterity prior to the application of the Intervention is 10.03 which reduced to 8.73 with a p-value of <0.001 which is considered as highly statistically significant. Which in turn depicts that the Core stabilization exercises improve the fine motor skills in Dentists.

Table 3: Post treatment comparison of MMT and Finger Dexterity

		Mean	N	SD	SD Error Mean	P value
MMT	Post	4.20	30	0.41	0.07	<0.001
Finger Dexterity	Post	8.73	30	1.01	0.18	

Figure 3: MMT and Finger Dexterity post treatment

Table 3 and Figure 3: Represents MMT and Finger dexterity post core stabilization exercises. Comparison of the above values is carried through an Unpaired t-test. The Unpaired t-test is applied when the two groups being compared are independent of each other as in this case the

comparison of MMT and Finger dexterity post treatment. The small p-value <0.001 indicates a significant difference between the two sets of values which is highly statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

Our study aimed to find the effect of core stabilization exercises on fine motor skills in dentists. This research work was conducted in our university with working Dentists. A total of 30 Dentists were selected and data was collected. Core muscle strength was analyzed using Manual Muscle Testing (MMT) and was graded accordingly. Fine motor was assessed using Finger Dexterity Board Test and the time was noted accordingly. Like other medical practitioners, dentists engage in challenging tasks requiring accuracy and concentration. However, these activities frequently impose significant stress on their bodies. The use of vibrating tools, the requirement of fine motor skills, and the sustained static postures result in tension and stress especially in the neck, shoulders, and back. Research indicates that a large proportion of dental professionals suffer from Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs), with estimates suggesting that 64-93% of dentists experience these disorders, and a similar prevalence is noted among dental students (5–7). According to a study dentists often perform manual scaling, a procedure that requires high force and precision to remove hard calculus from teeth in confined spaces. The constant need for exact hand movements places significant stress on the hands and wrists. Similarly, when dentists work in awkward postures, they often experience muscle fatigue and discomfort in the upper body, which may progress to chronic conditions if not addressed (1). This is compounded by the fact that dentists must remain in a seated position for prolonged periods, often resulting in static contraction of the spinal muscles, leading to fatigue and discomfort. The significant occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders in dental students highlights the necessity of focusing on posture and ergonomics at the beginning of a dental career. Dental students are particularly susceptible as they are still developing the skills necessary for effective manual dexterity and bi-manual coordination, which places additional strain on their bodies (8,9). Another study suggests that one of the key aspects of dental practice is manual dexterity, the ability to perform fine motor tasks with precision. Dentists rely mainly on manual dexterity to execute complex procedures such as drilling, filling, and scaling. These tasks often require the dentists to use both hands simultaneously- one for the procedure and the other to assist with positioning the instruments or mirrors. This is referred to as bi-manual coordination, which, like manual dexterity, demands a high level of skill and precision (10).

According to Patil S, Mahajan, core stability is equally important as manual dexterity in dentists. Core stability indicates the capacity of the lumbopelvic area to sustain a stable posture, facilitating optimal functioning of both the upper and lower limbs. The core muscles form the basis for the movement of the arms and legs (12). This is particularly important in dentistry, where dentists must maintain a stable trunk while executing precise movements with their hands.

Research supports the idea that core stabilization exercises can improve postural control and reduce the risk of musculoskeletal disorders in dental professionals. Core exercises have been shown to enhance trunk stability, which in turn can improve the precision and efficiency of movements in the upper extremities (13).

Furthermore, the link between core stability and motor skills in the upper extremities is supported by the kinetic chain model, which suggests that stability in a particular area of the body affects the functioning of other parts. This implies that improving core stability could directly benefit the fine motor skills required for dental procedures, ultimately enhancing the quality of care provided to the patients (14). Implementing core stabilization exercises as a part of dental professionals' training programs could therefore be a preventive measure against the development of MSDs.

Moreover, dentists should be educated on the importance of taking regular breaks and changing positions to reduce the impact of prolonged static postures. Incorporating physical exercises, such as stretching and strengthening routines including core stabilization exercises, into daily practice can also help prevent the buildup of muscle tension and maintain high standards of care for the patients. As research indicates, improving ergonomics can not only help prevent injuries but also enhance overall job satisfaction and patient care (4,5).

The study found a significant improvement in fine motor skills following the application of core stabilization exercises in dentists, indicating that enhanced core strength positively influences fine motor skills.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it concludes that there is a significant improvement in core strength and fine motor skills among dentists following the application of core stabilization exercises. The results suggest that enhancing core stability positively impacts the precision and dexterity required for fine motor tasks, as evidenced by improved performance on Finger Dexterity Test Board.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest

FUNDING

This research dose not received any external funding.

DATA AVAILIBILITY

Data of this study will be available with formal request to the principal investigator with the correspondence through email.

REFERENCES-

1. Halkai KR, Halkai RS, Sulgante S, Sanadi RM, Ara SA, Zainab H, et al. Work-related musculoskeletal disorders among dentists and their prevention through ergonomic interventions - A systematic review. *Int J Occup Saf Health*. 2022 Mar 13;12(2):125–39.
2. Benjamin SD, Manickavelu P, K M. Impact of Pinch Strength Training along with Postural Education on Upper Extremity Functional Performance among Dentist. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2021 May 21;11:241–7.
3. TekiN D, Köksal M. The Relation of The Duration of Work in Dentists with Postural Problems, Range of Motion and Pain. *Bezmialem Sci*. 2020 Jan 28;8(1):31–8.
4. McLaren W, Parrott L. Do dental students have acceptable working posture? *Br Dent J*. 2018 Jul;225(1):59–67.
5. Dable RA, Wasnik PB, Yeshwante BJ, Musani SI, Patil AK, Nagmode SN. Postural Assessment of Students Evaluating the Need of Ergonomic Seat and Magnification in Dentistry. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc*. 2014 Dec;14(Suppl 1):51–8.
6. Rafeemanesh E, Jafari Z, Kashani FO, Rahimpour F. A study on job postures and musculoskeletal illnesses in dentists. [cited 2024 Dec 19]; Available from: <https://ijomeh.eu/A-study-on-job-postures-and-musculoskeletal-illnesses-in-dentists,2174,0,2.html>
7. Gaowgzeh RA, Chevidikunnan MF, Al Saif A, El-Gendy S, Karrouf G, Al Senany S. Prevalence of and risk factors for low back pain among dentists. *J Phys Ther Sci*. 2015 Sep;27(9):2803–6.
8. Ng A, Hayes MJ, Polster A. Musculoskeletal Disorders and Working Posture among Dental and Oral Health Students. *Healthcare*. 2016 Jan 23;4(1):13.

9. Perceived musculoskeletal symptoms among dental students in the clinic work environment: *Ergonomics*: Vol 51 , No 4 - Get Access [Internet]. [cited 2024 Dec 19]. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00140130701728277>
10. Uziel N, Lugassy D, Ghanaym K, Meari H, Brosh T. Impact of physical and mental training on dental students' fine motor skills. *J Oral Rehabil*. 2023;50(8):698–705.
11. Imam SZ. *Manual Dexterity: An Important Tool for Dentists*. 2019;
12. Patil S, Mahajan A. Effect of Graded Plank Protocol on Core Stability in Sedentary Dentists. 2020;(2).
13. Miyake Y, Kobayashi R, Kelepecz D, Nakajima M. Core exercises elevate trunk stability to facilitate skilled motor behavior of the upper extremities. *J Bodyw Mov Ther*. 2013 Apr 1;17(2):259–65.
14. Güngörenler C, Şimşek T. The Effect of Core Stabilization Exercises on Upper Extremity Motor Skills in Overweight and Obese Children: Quasi-Experimental Controlled Study. *Türkiye Klin Pediatri Derg* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Aug 23];32(2). Available from: <https://avesis.deu.edu.tr/yayin/6b6045a4-af99-4ef3-989a-6f20a694986f/the-effect-of-core-stabilization-exercises-on-upper-extremity-motor-skills-in-overweight-and-obese-children-quasi-experimental-controlled-study>.
15. Effects of core stabilization exercise and strengthening exercise on proprioception, balance, muscle thickness and pain related outcomes in patients with subacute nonspecific low back pain: a randomized controlled trial | *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders* [Internet]. [cited 2024 Aug 16]. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12891-021-04858-6>
16. Kim B, Yim J. Core Stability and Hip Exercises Improve Physical Function and Activity in Patients with Non-Specific Low Back Pain: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Tohoku J Exp Med*. 2020;251(3):193–206.
17. Areeudomwong P, Buttagat V. Comparison of Core Stabilisation Exercise and Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation Training on Pain-related and Neuromuscular Response Outcomes for Chronic Low Back Pain: A Randomised Controlled Trial. *Malays J Med Sci MJMS*. 2019 Nov;26(6):77–89.
18. Dydik AM, Sapra A. Williams Back Exercises. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 26]. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK551558/>